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Investigation of Graphene/Silicon-di Oxide/Gallium Arsenide Based MIS Solar Cell Using Silvaco TCAD

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Solar cell based on Schottky junction exhibits lower open circuit voltage and lower conversion efficiency because of their higher dark saturation current. This saturation current can be reduced by inserting an insulating material in the Schottky junction which rises the barrier height for the dark current. However, the insulating material must be thin enough to ensure the tunneling of photo-generated current. The resulting structure is commonly known as metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) solar cell. This work focuses such a MIS solar cell, which has been implemented and investigated thoroughly using Silvaco TCAD software. In this proposed cell, graphene serves as Transparent conducting layer as well as the anode, n-doped GaAs act as the semiconductor and silicon-di-oxide plays the rule of insulator. The simulation results show that the proposed MIS solar cell offer a significant increase in open circuit voltage as well as power conversion efficiency.

Keywords: MIS solar cell, Schottky junction, conversion efficiency, dark saturation current, graphene.

1. Introduction

For decades, scientists and engineers have focused on developing highly efficient solar cells in order to meet the increasing renewable energy demand for sustainable development (Majumdar,2012). Till to date, a number of structures based on noble metal nanoparticles(Sheldon, 2014) as well as materials like carbon(Li,2010) perovskitesand organic(Kazim, 2015) are developed besides the conventional p-n junction based solar cells to achieve high efficiency. Because of excellent electrical properties such as extremely high carrier mobility (Mei,2014) and micro-scale ballistic transport (Maiaugree, 2013), optical properties such as 2.3% absorption of visible light(Shen, 2013), excellent thermal conductivity (Geim,2009)and high mechanical strength (Mayorov,2011), the two-dimensional material graphene draws the researchers' attention in the development of high-performance solar cell. Graphene put over semiconductor forms a Schottky diode that can be utilized for solar cell applications. Most interestingly, the barrier height of this Schottky diode is adjustable unlike the traditional Schottky diodes, as Fermi level of both graphene and the semiconductor can be tuned independently- a feature that makes the graphene/semiconductor Schottky diode based solar cells an attractive solution to meet the need of high efficiency.

Vazquez-Menaetal. reporteda MIS solar cell of 1.9% efficiency which used thinAulayergatedgraphene/zincphosphidebased structure. This reported value is low when considered with relatively large bandgap of zinc phosphide(1.5eV). A conversion efficiency of 5.6% has been achieved in a graphene/InPheterostructuresolarcell, where the Fermilevelofgraphenehas been tuned bythegatingeffect (Balandin,2008). Thestateof art PCE of

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graphene/semiconductor Schottky diode is 15.6% as achieved in graphene/Si system. Among all these semiconductors, GaAs has a suitable direct band gap of 1.42 eV (Shockley, 1961) and high electron mobility ($8000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 300K (Vorobev, 1971)), making it self one of the best candidates for high performance solar cells. However, one reported conversion efficiency for graphene/GaAs solar cell is only 1.95%, which does not reflect the advantages of graphene/GaAs system for high efficient solar cell (Jie, 2013)

In this work, we have designed a graphene/GaAs based MIS solar cell using Silvaco TCAD software. The proposed structure shows a significant increase in the open circuit voltage and conversion efficiency over the reported values.

2. Theory

Figure 1(a): Schottky junction cell structure

Figure 1(b): Band diagram of Schottky junction cell

Fig. 1(a) shows a traditional Schottky junction based solar cell structure. The Schottky junction is formed with metal-like graphene and GaAs semiconductor, where GaAs is doped as n-type so that the graphene work function (4.55 eV) is higher than that of the n-doped GaAs. Fig.1(b) displays the energy band diagram for this structure, where ϕ_B is the barrier height and can be determined from the difference of work functions of graphene and n-GaAs and V_{bi} is the built-in potential, for which an electric field is created across the depletion region formed near the metal-semiconductor interface. The electric field created by the Schottky junction is responsible for the photo-generated current J_{ph} flow through the solar cell. However, owing to the lower barrier height, the dark current is higher than that obtained in a p-n junction based solar cell as well as strongly dependent on temperature, which is evident from Eqn. (1).

$$J_0 = A T^2 e^{-\frac{q\phi_B}{kT}} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, J_0 is the dark saturation current, A is the Richardson's constant, K is the Boltzmann's constant and T is the temperature in Kelvin. Usually in p-n junction, the value of the dark saturation current is $<10^{-10}$ A, whereas, in Schottky junction the same is $>10^{-10}$ A. J_0 becomes even higher as the temperature increases [Eqn. (1)]. However, J_0 has an adverse effect on the open circuit voltage, which can be seen from Eqn. (2).

$$V_{oc} = \frac{kT}{q} \ln \left(1 + \frac{J_{ph}}{J_0} \right) \dots \dots (2)$$

Where, increase in J_0 decreases the open circuit voltage, V_{oc} . Since J_0 in Schottky junction is lowered from that of p-n junction by orders of magnitude, a drastic reduction in the open circuit voltage is observed in the Schottky junction based solar cell in comparison with the p-n junction based solar cell. Moreover, the open circuit voltage becomes worsened in Schottky junction solar cell when temperature

increases. However, open circuit voltage is directly related with the power conversion efficiency as

$$\eta_{conv} = FF \frac{V_{oc}J_{sc}}{P_{opt}} 100\% \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where η_{conv} is the conversion efficiency, FF is the fill factor, J_{sc} is the short circuit density and P_{opt} is the incident optical power density. Therefore, the Schottky junction solar cell exhibits a lower conversion efficiency than a p-n junction solar cell.

An improvement can be made to reduce this dark saturation current in order to increase the open circuit voltage as well as the conversion efficiency. An insulating oxide layer can be inserted between the graphene and GaAs layer to increase the effective barrier height. However, the insulating layer must be thin enough (> 2 nm) to enhance the tunneling of photo-generated current J_{ph} as well as to reduce the dark current J_0 . The new structure thus formed is termed as Metal-Insulator-Semiconductor (MIS) junction. In our work, we have used a thin layer of SiO_2 between graphene and GaAs. The improved structure as well as its band diagram are shown in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b) respectively.

Figure 2(a): Schottky junction with MIS cell structure

Figure 2(b): Band diagram of junction with MIS cell

3. Structure

In this work, a graphene-based MIS solar cell as shown in Fig.2(a) has been implemented using Atlas of Sivaco TCAD software. Graphene is chosen as the TCO as well as anode, since it is a semi-metal ($E_g = 0$ eV) with high transmittance and low resistivity. The work function of graphene is 4.55 eV and it can be used as anode as well as trans-conducting layer. In order to reduce the carrier loss due to back surface recombination, an n-ZnO has been appended after the n-GaAs layer to serve as back surface field (BSF) layer. Finally, an n-doped GaAs is placed at the bottom as substrate, which provides the mechanical support for the whole solar cell structure. The thickness and the doping level of all the layers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Layer, Material and Thickness for Proposed Graphene/Gaas MIS Solar Cell Structure

Layer	Material	Thickness	Doping
TCO	Gr	5 nm	-
Insulator	SiO_2	1 nm	-
Absorber	GaAs	5 μm	$1e16$
BSF	ZnO	5 nm	$1e16$
Substrate	GaAs	0.5 μm	$1e15$

4. Results and Discussion

In this section the simulation results of the proposed MIS solar cell has been presented, analyzed and also, compared with Schottky junction solar cell. All the simulations have been carried out using the Atlas tool of the Silvaco TCAD software.

Fig. 3(a) shows the current-voltage (J-V) characteristics of both the MIS and Schottky junction solar cells. The said graph plots the cathode current against the anode voltage. From this curve, it is evident that the MIS solar cell shows a higher open circuit voltage than the Schottky junction solar cell, as expected owing to the increase of barrier height at the graphene/GaAs interface for the insertion of thin layer of SiO_2 between them. The reduction of the short circuit current for the proposed solar cell can be attributed to the tunneling mechanism of the photo-generated current through the increased barrier. However, this reduction of the short circuit current does not adversely affect the solar cell efficiency as seen from the power vs. voltage curve shown in Fig. 3(b). From Fig. 3(b), it is obvious that the power of the MIS solar cell is much higher than the Schottky junction solar cell for anode voltages greater than 0.2 volt. For anode voltages less than 0.2 V, the power is slightly less, which is due to the lowered current in the MIS solar cell. The maximum power for the proposed solar cell is almost 2 times higher than the Schottky junction solar cell at an increased anode voltage.

Fig.3(a); anode voltage vs Cathode Current Fig.3(b): Anode voltage vs Power

A comparative study of performance parameters of both the MIS and Schottky junction solar cells can be made from Table 2. First, the short circuit current which is almost 16% lower in the MIS structure than the Schottky junction structure. The open circuit voltage in the MIS solar cell is more than 2.5 times than in the Schottky structure. The maximum power of the MIS solar cell is increased by more than 100%, whereas, the current and voltage corresponding to this maximum power is decreased by almost 12% and is increased by more than two times respectively. The fill factor is decreased by almost 8% in the proposed MIS solar cell, which reflects the carrier loss in the tunneling mechanism of the photo-generation current.

Table 2: Comparison of electrical parameters between Schottky junction and MIS cells

Parameter	Schottky Junction Cell	MIS Cell
Short Circuit Current, J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	54.8318	45.7793
Open Circuit Voltage, V_{oc} (V)	0.2130	0.5225
Maximum Power Current, J_m (mA/cm ²)	46.5001	40.0726
Maximum Power Voltage, V_m (V)	0.161	0.355
Fill Factor, FF (%)	64.0924	59.4745
Conversion Efficiency, η (%)	7.4838	14.2201

5. Conclusion

This work presents an Atlas-simulation based analysis for a metal-insulator-semiconductor (MIS) structured solar cell using graphene as metal, silicon dioxide as insulator and n-GaAs as the semiconductor. In order to observe the superiority of the proposed solar cell, the performance parameters are compared with Schottky junction based solar cell, where only insulator layer is absent. Both these solar cells have used a ZnO-BSF layer and a GaAs-substrate to enhance their performances. TCAD simulation results show that the proposed MIS solar cell has higher open circuit voltage (almost 2.5 times) as well as higher conversion efficiency (almost double) than that obtained in the Schottky junction solar cell. It can be inferred from this analysis that the enhancement of both open circuit voltage and the power conversion efficiency is solely due to the increase of the effective barrier height at the graphene/GaAs interface.

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